

DAMAGE BASED FATIGUE LIFE MODELING FOR BRITTLE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Fiber reinforced composites are usually notch insensitive. Damage in composite, under static loading is usually due to several concurrent fracture modes as fiber failure, matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding, fibre pull-out and delamination. These mechanisms reduce the material load carrying capability. In fatigue this situation can be even more complicated. In brittle composite systems where all constituents have brittle behavior with no dissipation processes other than the creation of new fracture surfaces - they exhibit a strong connection between the first damaging fatigue cycle and the subsequent damage evolution. In addition, damage produced during the first cycle can be directly related to the one produced due to monotonic loading. In the present paper a fatigue damage model for brittle composites is presented. The effect of complex damage state was examined in terms of stiffness loss as a function of the accumulated strain during cycling. The model, developed on phenomenological basis, has been verified on several composite systems such as unidirectional ceramic matrix and cross-ply polymeric composites.

KEYWORDS: fatigue life model, brittle composite, stiffness loss, damage

INTRODUCTION

Prediction of fatigue life in brittle composites where only microcracks dominate the overall dissipation characteristics remains an important challenge as growth laws based on fracture mechanics for single cracks are inadequate. Due to the complex damage modes that occur in a composite material under static or cycling loading, it is appropriate to address the complex damage states where several basic fracture types such as matrix cracks, fibre breaks, delamination, and fibre-matrix disbonds and their mutual interactions are accounted for, particularly, in developing life models. The best way to investigate fatigue effects on composite materials is to assess the degradation of the material properties such as elastic moduli as a function of the number of cycles [1-3]. A direct consequence of distributed microcrack-type damage is tensorial stiffness property change in composites.

There is an important connection between the first cycle damage and subsequent damage evolution in fatigue in laminated composites. The damage that occurs in the first cycle is no different than that which occurs during monotonic response. In order to clearly understand the implication of this initial damage, it is important to develop the link between monotonic damage and fatigue damage to develop proper fatigue life models. Monotonic response of unidirectional CMCs have been studied extensively by a number of researchers [4-12].

Proportional limit of unidirectional CMCs have been associated with matrix cracking and subsequent nonlinear behavior has been identified to be due to progressive fiber failure [9,10]. Matrix cracking in CMCs has been the subject of in-depth investigation by researchers as well [12,13]. Continuum damage mechanics models can be used to predict the stiffness loss in these composites due to the presence of damage which are typically microcrack entities such as matrix cracks, fiber matrix disbonds and fiber cracks [3]. Monotonic damage evolution and subsequent modeling of the stiffness changes using continuum approaches were investigated for the hybrid composite [14]. Cyclic damage has been characterized by a number of researchers for glass matrix composites which confirm that a combination of damage such as matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding and fiber fracture depending on the lay-up of the composite [15]. Polymeric composites (PMCs) brittle matrices such as epoxy also can be categorized as brittle composites because of the nature of dissipation characteristics due to distributed matrix cracks. Other PMCs also show brittle characteristics as plastic deformation is suppressed at the microstructural level as much of the load is carried by carbon fibers. Microcracking in toughened epoxies and in thermoplastic matrices are also dominant dissipation mechanisms precluding plastic deformation that occurs readily in bulk matrices. As far as distributed microcracking is concerned in PMCs during fatigue, they can be categorized as brittle where energy dissipation is primarily controlled by free surface creation.

MODELING ASPECTS

Fig. 1 shows the data scatter for several fatigue tests performed with ceramic matrix composites [16] at room temperature with the same R-ratio and frequency and σ_{\max} . In order to arrange experimental data in a more meaningful way, the number of cycles has been normalized by N_f . This representation allows one to separate the scatter relative to N_f and to underline the main feature of the fatigue damage evolution law. In this case, it is possible to identify a lower bound for the degradation of the moduli.

The fact that brittle composites are very sensitive, in terms of accumulated damage, to the very first cycle is indicative of a high sensitivity to the applied strain. It has been seen that it is more appropriate to approach composites in terms of strain instead of stress, since due to the non-homogeneity of the micro-structure, strains have to be the same while stresses are different in matrix and in the fiber.

If the strains applied in the first few cycles are high enough to introduce damage in the microstructure, this will lead to stiffness loss. The subsequent cycles will see a progressive evolution of the initiated damage state that will develop more gradually up to the moment of final fracture. It is very difficult to develop an accurate model, defined on micro-mechanical basis that is able to predict the physical evolution of complex damage states. The main features can be obtained from the fatigue tests in terms of the shape of the stiffness reduction trend. Many authors pointed out that brittle materials such as glass or glass-ceramic materials show practically no range of fatigue behavior that results in a crack of the order of an existing flaw size growing instantaneously. A number of authors [15,17] suggested that fatigue cycling does not lead to new damage modes in the composites.

If fatigue cycling does not introduce additional damage modes other than the growth of the already existing complex damage state, it follows that the evolution features related to the fatigue process are all contained in the shape of the distribution of the fatigue data. Furthermore, cyclic damage measurements taken at different cycles should fall on the same

static damage curve shown in Fig.2. The last observation has been verified by plotting damage measurements taken at different number of cycles versus the total strain applied during the cycling. When a specimen is cycled in stress control, due to creation of new surfaces, the true applied strain increases with the number of cycles as shown in Fig. 3. The progressive material damage is illustrated in Fig. 4. The applied strain is partially recovered elastically in the cycle but there is a contribution that accumulates as ratchetting, due to incomplete closure of cracked surfaces during unloading.

The relation that describes the damage evolution via modulus reduction in the applied loading direction, E_D/E_0 , as a function of the number of cycles, have to be bounded between 0 and 1 for a number of cycles comprised between 1 and N_f . The following relation :

$$\frac{E_D}{E_0} = B(\varepsilon) \cdot \left[1 - \frac{\ln(N)}{\ln(N_f)} \right]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

seem to be appropriate to describe the experimental data trend. When the number of cycle reaches N_f , i.e. the number of cycles at fracture, the ratio E_D/E_0 goes to zero. E with subscripts D and 0 represent current and initial stiffnesses, respectively. Note that $D = 1 - E_D/E_0$. When $N=1$, then the amount of damage at the first cycle is determined by the imposed strain field in the material. In fact only if the strain level is high enough to produce damage in the first place, then further damage will develop during cycling.

To determine the amplitude constant B, it is sufficient to observe that the first cycle, if the strain rate is not extremely high, is similar to a static load ramp up to the imposed maximum strain. For this reason, the amount of damage produced in the first cycle have to be related to the static damage curve as suggested by the authors [14]:

$$B(\varepsilon) = (1 - D_0) - (D_{cr} - D_0) \left[1 - \frac{\ln(\varepsilon / \varepsilon_{th})}{\ln(\varepsilon_f / \varepsilon_{th})} \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (2)$$

that substituted in Eqn. 1 leads to:

$$\frac{E_D}{E_0} = \left((1 - D_0) - (D_{cr} - D_0) \frac{\ln[e / e_{th}]}{\ln[e_f / e_{th}]} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \left[1 - \frac{\ln[N]}{\ln[N_f]} \right]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (3)$$

In addition to CMCs, the model can be applied to PMCs as the fatigue damage process in these materials is dominated by matrix cracking which manifests as stiffness loss as a function of fatigue cycles. As in the case of CMCs, the damage in PMCs in terms of matrix cracks and/or fiber cracks are the energy dissipation events that are completely controlled by creation of new surfaces only. Consequently, based on damage processes at work in fatigue, both types of composites exhibit brittle behavior. Working with data from literature [18-19] and analyzing them using the approach discussed earlier, the proposed fatigue damage model can predict the trend in damage evolution as shown in Figures 5-6.

CONCLUSIONS

Damage in CMCs as well as PMCs are strain controlled. More particularly, magnitude of damage as manifested by stiffness loss is dependent on the strain experienced by the composite as described by Eqn. 3. The fatigue life model presented requires the evaluation of a number of parameters such as ϵ_{th} , ϵ_{cr} and m which can be obtained through a static test. Only two parameters, exponent β and the number of cycle at fracture N_f , have to be determined using fatigue data. Anyway, only few tests performed at two or three different stress levels will be sufficient to identify the parameters in a proper way. The nature of damage evolution as dictated by stiffness loss during fatigue can be cast in a functional form that captures the essence of strain controlled damage. Fatigue life for a given reduction in stiffness can be estimated from the functional form if nominal final life is known from limited experimental data. This approach seems to work well for both CMCs and PMCs. Hence, this basic life prediction model for fatigue that captures the essence of the trend in fatigue data in brittle composites shows significant promise.

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REFERENCES

1. Highsmith, A. L. and Reifsnider, K. L., "Stiffness-Reduction Mechanisms in Composite Laminates," in *Damage in Composite Materials*, ASTM STP 775, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, 1982, pp.103.
2. Laws, N., Dvorak, G.J., and Hejazi, M., "Stiffness Changes in Unidirectional Composites Caused by Crack Systems," *J. Mechanics of Materials*, vol.2, 1983, p.123
3. Talreja, R., *Fatigue of Composite Materials*, Technical University of Denmark, 1985.
4. Prewo, K.M., "Tension and Flexural Strength of Silicon Carbide Fiber-reinforced Glass Ceramics", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 21, 1986, p. 3590.
5. Prewo, K. M., "Advanced Characterization of SiC Fiber reinforced Glass Matrix Composites", Office of Naval Research Contract N00014-81-C-0571, Interim report, June, 1983.
6. Zawada, L.P., Butkus, L.M. and Hartman, G.A., "Room Temperature Tensile and Fatigue properties of SiC Fiber-Reinforced Aluminosilicate Glass", *Ceramic Engineering Science and Proceedings*, Vol. 11, 1990, p. 1592.
7. Nardone, V.C. and Prewo, K.M., "Tensile Performance of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Glass", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 23, 1988, p. 168.
8. Newaz, G.M., Brust, F.W., Jarmon, D.C. and Cairo, R.R., "Deformation, Failure and Mechanical Response Modeling in Dual Fiber CMC", Presented at the Annual ACS Meeting, Cocoa beach, Florida, January, 1994.
9. Rousseau, C.Q., "Monotonic and Cyclic Behavior of a SiC/CAS Composite", *ASTM STP 1080*, J.M. Kennedy, H.M. Mouller, and W.S. Johnson Eds., 1990, p. 136.

10. Prewo, K.M., Johnson, B. and Starett, S., "Silicon Carbide Fiber-Reinforced Glass-Ceramics", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol.24, 1989, p.1373.
11. Sbaizero, O. and Evans, A.G., "Tensile and Shear properties of Laminated Ceramic Matrix Composites", *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 69, # 6, 1986, p. 481.
12. Aveston, and J.Kelly, "Theory of Multiple Fracture of Fibrous Composites", *Journal of Materials Science*, 1973, Vol.8, p. 352.
13. Budiansky, B., Hutchinson, J.W., and Evans, A.G., "Matrix Fracture in Fiber-Reinforced Ceramics", *Journal of Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Vol. 34. p. 35.
14. Bonora, N. and Newaz, G., "Modeling Damage Evolution in a Hybrid Ceramic Matrix Composite Under Static Tensile Loading", accepted for publication in *J. Engineering Materials and Technology*, ASME, Nov., 1996.
15. Karandikar, P.G. and Chou, T.W., "Microcracking and Elastic Moduli Reductions in Unidirectional Nicalon-CAS Composites Under Cyclic Fatigue Loading", *Proceeding of the 16th Annual Conference on Composites and Advanced Ceramics*, Cocoa Beach, Florida, Jan., 1992.
16. Newaz, G.M. and Bonora, N., "Fatigue Life Modeling in Hybrid CMCs," in *Thermal and Mechanical Test methods and Behavior of Continuous Fiber Ceramic Composites*, ASTM STP 1309, M.G.Jenkins, S.T. Gonczy, E. Lara-Curizio, N.E Ashbaugh and L.P. Zawada, Eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1996.
17. Evans, A.G. and Fuller, E.R., "Crack Propagation in Ceramic Materials under Cyclic Loading Conditions", *Metall. Trans.* 5, (1974), p.27.
18. Charewicz A. and I.M. Daniel, "Damage Mechanisms and Accumulation in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," in *Composite Material: Fatigue and Fracture*, ASTM STP 907, H.T.Hahn Ed., 1986, pp. 274-297.
19. Bonora, N., Marchetti, M. and Millela, P.P., "Theoretical Forecasting and Experimental Validation of Damage Tolerance and Accumulation in Glass/Epoxy laminates", *J. of reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol II, 1992, pp. 56-81.

FIG. 1 -- Different stiffness loss versus number of cycle for similar maximum applied cyclic stress

FIG. 2 -- Comparison between static and fatigue damage and proposed law.

FIG. 3 -- Scheme of residual strain, due to damage, accumulation process under fatigue loading.

FIG. 4 -- Stress-strain material data curves during cycling.

Fig. 5 - Damage in Graphite/Epoxy $[0,90_2]_s$ laminate under fatigue loading: comparison between experimental data and the present model, (data from Charewicz and Daniel, 1986)

Fig. 6 - Damage in S-Glass/Epoxy $[90_4,0]_s$ laminate under fatigue loading: comparison between experimental data and the present model, (data from Bonora et al., 1992).